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GLOBALLASHUV HODISASI VA GLOBALLASHUV**GLOBALIZATION PHENOMENON AND
GLOBALISM****ФЕНОМЕН ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ И ГЛОБАЛИЗМ****ANNOTATSIYA**

Ushbu maqolada hozirgi zamonda dunyo so'nggi yuz yillik ichida yuz bergan jamiyat hayoti barcha jabhalarining faol integratsiyalashuvi natijasida sezilarli darajada o'zgarganligi va yaxlit bir butun organizmga aylanganligi bayon etilgan. Buning oqibati o'laroq, ayrim xalqlar va butun insoniyatning ijtimoiy ongida global jarayonlar va ularning ta'sirida yuzaga kelgan umumiy (dunyo miqyosidagi) muammolar bilan belgilangan jiddiy o'zgarishlar yuz bera boshlaganligi va jahon hamjamiyati o'z rivojlanishining yangi bosqichiga qadam qo'ygani, u avvalgi bosqichlardan nafaqat o'zgarishlar miqyosi, balki faollik darajasi va universal xususiyati bilan ham farq qilishi bayon etiladi.

ANNOTATION

This article describes the fact that in modern times the world has changed significantly as a result of the active integration of all aspects of the life of society that have occurred in the last hundred years and has become a holistic whole organism. As a consequence, it is stated that serious changes began to occur in the social consciousness of some peoples and all of humanity, marked by global processes and common (worldwide) problems that have arisen under their influence, and the world community has entered a new stage of its development, which differs from the previous stages not only in the scale of changes, but also

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье рассказывается о том, что в наше время мир значительно изменился и стал единым целым организмом в результате активной интеграции всех сторон жизни общества, которая произошла за последнее столетие. Следствием этого становится то, что в общественном сознании отдельных народов и всего человечества начинают происходить существенные изменения, обусловленные глобальными процессами и возникшими под их влиянием общемировыми (общемировыми) проблемами, и мировое сообщество вступает в новый этап своего развития, который отличается от предыдущих этапов не только масштабами изменений, но и уровнем активности и универсальным характером.

KALIT SO'ZLAR

globallashuv, globalistika, jahon, muammolar, vaziyatlar, fan, yechimlar

KEYWORDS

globalization, globalism, world, problems, situations, science, solutions

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

глобализация, Глобалистика, мир, проблемы, ситуации, наука, решения

INTRODUCTION

To produce a clearer picture of the present, it is important to assume that until the beginning of the 20th century, world history consisted mainly of civilizations that developed independently and did not seriously affect each other. In modern times, the world has changed significantly as a result of the active integration of all aspects of the life of society, which has occurred in the last hundred years, and has become a holistic whole organism. As a result of this, serious changes began to occur in the social consciousness of some peoples and all of humanity, marked by global processes and common (worldwide) problems that arose under their influence. It turned out that the world community has entered a new stage of its development, it differs from the previous stages not only in the scale of changes, but also in the level of activity and universal nature.

This whole set of changes, as well as their causes, was the subject of globalization in the 1990s (lot. globus - Earth Sphere). Globalization is the process of formation, universalization of structures, connections and relationships that are unique for the entire planet Earth in various aspects of society's life. Also globalization is characterized by the contiguity of global space, single World Economy, general environmental interaction, global communications, etc.

A large number of efforts to realize the latest trends in World Development led to the emergence of globalism, an area of interdisciplinary scientific research aimed at identifying the essence, trends and causes of globalization processes, global problems that arise under their influence and realizing the consequences of these processes. In a broader sense, the term "globalism" is used to refer to scientific, philosophical, cultural and applied research on various aspects of globalization and global problems, including their results, as well as practical activities for their implementation on economic, social and political fronts, both at the level of certain states and internationally.

It should be noted that globalism is not usually among certain disciplines that arise as a result of the stratification of scientific knowledge or at the junction of related disciplines. At the time of its formation lie the opposite processes—the processes of integration characteristic of modern science. Globalism is such a facet of research and knowledge, where different disciplines are inextricably linked with each other, each from the point of view of its subject and method, analyzes different aspects of globalization, studying global problems as a separate and integrated system, proposing their solutions.

Globalism as an independent scientific direction and field of social practice began to take shape in the late 1960s, but the objective foundations for its emergence had arisen much earlier.

MAIN PART

The first manifestations of current globalization processes can be encountered from the end of the 15th century, and by the beginning of the 19th century it had gained real importance in practice. It was a period of great geographical discoveries that ultimately led to the formation of a single geographical, to some extent economic and political world space. Geocentric approaches to understanding the world in the same period are heliocentric gave way to approaches, while humanity finally managed to correctly interpret the alternation of day and night. Science broke away from philosophy and gave a strong impetus to the accumulation of knowledge and the development of technology, causing the development of Science and technology and the industrial revolution to occur. The last mentioned events ultimately completely changed the nature-changing possibilities of Man and his relationship with the environment.

Having theoretically and practically proven that the Earth's globe is in the form of a sphere (globe), humanity was the first in its history to reach the world level in trade and laid the foundation for international relations on a global scale. It was during this period that the first

transnational trading companies emerged. Soon, their activities went beyond the limits of pure trade, and they began to participate in the process of capturing and exploiting slaves, establishing plantations and settlements in the occupied territories, finally becoming the main executor of the colonial policies that their state was implementing.

All this also caused serious migration processes to occur. In particular, the colonists began to transport black slaves from Africa to America in a mass manner, thus completely changing its demographic. Therefore, it is possible to conclude that self-globalization is inextricably linked from the beginning with the economic, political and cultural life of different peoples.

By the beginning of the 17th century, Eastern and Western merchants had mastered vast territories and settled almost all over the world. In this way, they were the first in the history of mankind to establish the necessary foundations of a single global economic and political system and set the stage for the formation of this system.

Thus, the great geographical discoveries of the 15th and 16th centuries made a fundamental turn in the course of the development of world history and “led to a sharp, unprecedented expansion of European politics. The borders of the world have expanded to some extent. Competition in the struggle for the colonies was now added to the various conflicts between European countries”. Thus the foundation was laid for new international economic and political relations, the interaction of different cultures, and the expansion of Western European maritime states in different regions of the earth that they had discovered.

Fundamental globalization is associated with the occurrence of world-class contacts, structures and relationships. As a result of these processes, the world was permanently formed in almost all its aspects as a holistic whole organism. The first signs of such globalization, known as Fundamental, appeared in the second half of the

19th century, and by the middle of the 20th century it had become a full-fledged being.

At the same time, the economic division of the world was completed, and as a result of this, sharp international problems of a completely new nature arose, arising from the growing interdependence of different countries and peoples. These processes covered not only the economy, politics and social life, but also the means of communication and communication, as well as the spiritual front – culture, science and philosophy. Various international organizations, forums, congresses, congresses began to arise, which was also facilitated by the active development of communication and Mass Communication Media at that time.

Thus, in practice, the whole world became a field of fierce struggle and division of spheres of influence between powerful states and large monopolies, which ultimately led to the beginning of the first World War. In this war, a large number of peoples of the world participated directly or indirectly, since until this time, the economic and political dependence that arose on a global scale did not allow any large state of the planet to completely deviate from the war or at least its effects and consequences. This is a sign that from this period history has become not only the history of Europe or, say, a separate history of China, Russia, America, the West, the East, but also the history of mankind, that is, a literal world history.

Ultimately, in the period between the first and Second World Wars, globalization processes became more exaggerated. During this period, the main beliefs of globalization:

- a) increased anthropogenic influence on the biosphere and the transformation of man into a real “geological force”;
- b) the fact that mass culture begins to actively develop, first of all, in the field of film, music, literature, the production of large-scale consumer goods;
- c) the invention of television, over time it becomes the main promoter of popular culture and a symbol of globalization;

g) space and time were first manifested in straight take-offs, not intercontinental landings, on airships that were continuously “reduced” to indicators of human daily life.

But unresolved conflicts and increased general dependence led to the beginning of the largest and most continuous war in human history – World War II. This time, the worldwide war involved three-quarters of the Earth's population, with several times more casualties than the First World War.

In terms of the globalization of world-class processes, both of these wars were practically different stages of the same global war. The difference between them is visible only in quantitative indicators. In essence, both wars were aimed at solving the same issues – at re-dividing the whole and interconnected world, which took place at the beginning of the 20th century. The methods of conducting war were also almost one, and the difference was that the level and scale of technical equipment were several times higher in World War II, and the ideological influence was manifested in the multiple intensification of the previous war with the widespread use of either non-existent radio, telephone, or not yet well-developed aviation, maritime, rail, road transport communications and communications.

The Second World War, like the previous World War, had a number of universal consequences that became a characteristic feature of the post-war secular order. The most important among them was that the war stimulated research and practical work on the creation of a completely new type of weapon (atomic and reactive weapons).

In this period, their first samples were tested in combat and provided humanity with endless opportunities to turn the whole world into ruins and destroy all living things. The same achievements of the development of Science and technology later determined the essence and content of the arms race, which peaked during the “Cold War”, and practically demonstrated the fragility and contiguity of the planet in space.

Another consequence of the Second World War arose in the socio-political sphere of society's life, and it was manifested in the unprecedented growth of various international organizations. Among them, the United Nations (UN), undoubtedly, stands out. The integration processes in Europe also marked the end of the war, and the year 1946, which British Prime Minister Winston Churchill called for the formation of the United States of Europe, can be considered their number one.

The Nuremberg trials over the chief war criminals group and the main Nazi organizations were another important event and at the same time the first experience of worldwide cooperation in the field of legal regulation of international relations. This process was carried out by the first international military tribunal in history, established on August 8, 1945 by the victorious countries – the USSR, the United States, Great Britain and France-and was an important step towards the establishment of the current international court system. In the same period, the ideas of liberalism and democracy began to spread widely around the world, a set of serious studies and theoretical developments appeared, aimed at re-realizing the foundations of social existence, the moral foundations of society and the basic principles of Social Development.

The brilliance of globalization. The realization of global threats and globalization processes by broad segments of the population, as well as the reaction to the world community and the corresponding values, the formation of culture, lifestyle globalization

fertility is a characteristic of the stage. From the 1970s, globalization has moved to a new stage of its development and has become lush. At the same time, the development of the information and technology revolution accelerated, along with myth, religion, philosophy, science, ecology, global consciousness appeared as another form of social consciousness.

The brilliance of globalization has significantly changed the world market, the world economy has shown its peculiarities, providing an

opportunity to become stronger and more important than national farms. The following are important features of globalisation viability:

a) the emergence of the “resonance effect”, in which economic ups and downs go from one country to other countries and regions that are inextricably linked with it;

b) the creation of various goods and services world markets;

c) the formation of world prices for goods and services provided, they largely determine the policy of the national producers of goods and services in question.

In addition to the internationalization of the economy and the unification of the monetary role, the formation of a mass society and a corresponding mass culture has become a characteristic feature of surreal globalization and, to some extent, its legal product.

In the context of globalization, where, thanks to modern means of transport and communication, the factors of space and time have practically ceased to be important, language has become the last serious obstacle to the communication and communication of various peoples, economic, political, scientific, domestic, etc. The objective need for a generally accepted language has always existed, but in the era of progressive globalization, when the volumes of World Trade and the transfer of capital from one place to another have increased a lot, political relations have expanded to the global level, international public organizations, sports competitions, the tourist industry and the like have appeared, it has especially intensified. Today, English has become the language of intercultural communication for a number of objective reasons.

With the advent of the Internet in 1991, the world became more informationally remote. The computer revolution and the development of the Internet network gave rise to a new information space in which everything but borders existed.

The brilliance of globalization has also led to a significant change in politics. While bipolarity,

characterized by the fierce opposition of the two military-political blocs, which were in a state of “Cold War” until the 1990s, was considered the main feature of international relations, the situation changed completely with the disintegration of the socialist system.

In recent years, in addition to the activities of nation-states, the activity and influence of new, “non-traditional” subjects of international relations has grown significantly. These entities can freely compete with certain states according to their number, financial capabilities and political influence. Among these subjects of international relations, the most important are intergovernmental organizations, transnational corporations, international non-governmental organizations. Social movements such as the “Greens”, “alternatives”, antiglobalists have also gained widespread admiration.

The brilliance of globalization, in addition to making serious structural changes in culture, international relations and international law, has also created a strong need for significant changes in ethics, norms of behavior, attitudes towards values and goals. A completely new phenomenon has arisen-world public opinion, and the number of people on the planet who consider themselves world citizens has increased.

The world community has crossed the border of the new millennium and entered a completely new stage of its historical development. This stage is characterized by the transition from the dissolution and parochialism of world socio-political, economic and spiritual ties to their unity, integrity, uniqueness and globality.

The globalization processes under consideration have brought people new grief and new (global) problems arising from the internationalization of social life. As noted above, they were the product of quantitative and qualitative changes that took place over a long period of time in social development, as well as in the system of “society-nature”.

It should be noted that the current situation, which is characterized by the fact that the world community is not only more colorful, but also more controversial than before, has never been in history.

CONCLUSION

Science has always helped a person in solving difficult and complex tasks. It is with the help of science that most of what once seemed unattainable, beyond the level of human capabilities was achieved. It is for this reason that the first warnings that global problems pose a threat forced the self-centered people to turn their attention to science, and scientists to look for ways to solve these problems.

The peculiarity and novelty of the situation that has arisen is that while any specific problems can be studied within the framework of some science or a set of several disciplines, some disciplines are not capable of researching global problems consisting of a complex system that covers man, society and nature in their numerous interactions and interactions. Zero is the object of his research – the narrowness of the scope of certain disciplines to interpret this or that problem in the context of other global problems. Therefore, regardless of which specific tasks this or that science solves, a philosophical approach to the processes and phenomena associated with them, that is, to the whole situation, including ultimately the results obtained, is always a prerequisite for research.

Any particular science at a certain stage will need to one degree or another to philosophically understand its subject of research. It is impossible both to make fundamental discoveries and the development of science as a whole without such a broad approach to the subject of a particular science and the problems facing humanity.

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